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METHODS OF DETERMINING LIMITING DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF TWO-COMPONENT METALLIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The paper describes the methods of determining the limiting coefficient of distribution, as one of the main parameters for evaluating the efficiency of deep refining of metals by crystallization methods. Experimental, calculation and graphical methods of determining the limiting coefficients of distribution in metal systems for different types of solubility are described. The determination methods for systems with limited solubility of components in the solid phase and with extremely low solubility are considered. The calculations of this parameter are performed for binary systems based on Cd, Zn, Te, Zr, Hf, and Ti. The results of graphical methods of determining the limiting coefficient of distribution for such systems as Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge are presented.

Keywords: distribution coefficients, binary state diagrams, solubility of components, methods for determining limiting coefficient of distribution.

Introduction

During liquid-solid phase transitions for two-component systems, the interphase distribution coefficients (DC) of the components are important parameters. Therefore, when solving practical problems, there is often a need for an approximate estimate of unknown DC. Among the known DC, such as the effective (EFDC) k_{ef} and the equilibrium (EDC) k_{0B}^A , it is important for practical and computational applications (for example, for estimating the limiting solubility of poorly soluble components, calculating the solidus lines of binary eutectic systems, determining the thermodynamic parameters of the solubility of components, etc.) has the limiting coefficient of distribution (LCD) k_{0limB}^A . LCD characterizes the interphase distribution of the second component near the melting temperature of the main component, that is, with a low concentration of the impurity element. The value of this parameter provides a guideline for evaluating the efficiency of deep refining of metals by the method of directional crystallization

(DCr). The purpose of this paper is to review the methods of determining k_{0limB}^A and to provide examples of the application of these methods for the calculation of the limiting distribution coefficients for individual binary systems.

1. Characteristics of the distribution coefficients of two-component metallic systems

One of the methods of deep cleaning of metals at the final stage is DCr. An important parameter characterizing the behavior of an impurity during purification by the DCr method is the DC of the impurity. Based on the known values of DC, it is possible to pre-plan the crystallization purification process and estimate the achievable purity of the refined metal.

The definitions of the characteristics of EFDC, EDC, LCD were given, for example, in [1]. The EDC were determined by the thermodynamic properties of the main component A and impurities at a crystallization rate equal to or close to zero. The EDC values were found, as a rule, from double state diagrams (SD)

"base-impurity", or by extrapolation to zero crystallization rate of experimentally determined EFDC. The EFDC value is not an "invariant" of this specific system of substances, and for this reason, the values of k_{ef} for different systems and different DCr methods cannot be compared with each other and cannot be used to construct any dependencies, correlations, etc. When using the data of interphase DC in practice, it is necessary to be aware of their certain convention. The most complete information on DC of impurities in metals was given in monographs [1, 2].

The LDC of the impurity (k_{olimB}^A) is based on the value of k_{0B}^A when extrapolating the content of the impurity to its zero concentration, which characterizes the region of the ultrapure substance. In most cases, in the region of extremely dilute solutions, the liquidus and solidus lines of SD are not rectilinear, and the value of k_{0B}^A depends on the concentration of the impurity element. At the same limit reduction in the content of the impurity element k_{0B}^A will strive for its constant limit value k_{olimB}^A , the determination of which is one of the important experimental and theoretical tasks.

2. Experimental method of determining LDC

The frozen zone method described in [3] is suitable for experimental determination of EFDC. The experiment was carried out in an electron-beam apparatus for refining by zone melting. The molten zone was moved along the rod by approximately 25-30 mm and then allowed to solidify as quickly as possible by abruptly turning off the electron beam power. The zone passes were performed at different speeds. Transverse discs about 1 mm thick were cut from the samples, some from the "frozen zones" and others from a location near the front of the zone. To determine the concentration of impurities in the alloy, mass spectral, neutron activation and other methods of analysis were used. The concentration ratio gave the EFDC value. The EDC value was determined using the Burton-Prime-Slichter equation [4]. The thermodynamic calculation of the temperature dependence of EDC under the assumption of ideal behavior of the system was given in [1], in which the following expression was obtained:

$$\ln k_{0B}^A = \frac{T_{MA}}{T} \ln k_{olimB}^A - \frac{\Delta S_{MB}}{R} \left(\frac{T_{MA}}{T} - 1 \right), \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Diagrams of the state of systems A–B (schematically) with limited solubility of components in the solid phase (a) and with extremely low solubility (b).

where k_{olimB}^A is the LDC of component B in A; T_{MA} is the melting point of the main component A; T is the temperature of the liquidus line; R – universal gas constant; ΔS_{MB} is the melting entropy of component B.

It can be seen from the given expression that when $T \rightarrow T_{MA}$, the equilibrium DC passes into the limiting one, $k_{0B}^A \rightarrow k_{olimB}^A$. Having transformed (1) with respect to k_{olimB}^A , assuming that k_{0B}^A does not depend on temperature, it is possible to determine the value of LDC. Thus, from the procedure described above, we arrive at the determination of k_{olimB}^A by the experimental method. It will be shown below that when the temperature T deviates from T_{MA} by less than 10°C , that is, $\Delta T_{MA} < 10^\circ\text{C}$, k_{olimB}^A assumes its constant value, which no longer depends on temperature.

3. Calculation method of determining LDC

For calculations of k_{olimB}^A in metals, there is a well-known method of mathematical analysis of graphical extrapolation of the solidus and liquidus lines of SD at the point of their intersection at the melting temperature of the pure T_{MA} component, that is, when the impurity concentration tends to zero [1, 3, 5]. At the same time, it should be noted that different approaches to calculations have been developed for different solubility systems (Fig. 1). Figure 1 shows state diagrams of systems A–B with limited solubility of components in the solid phase (a) and with extremely low solubility (b).

3.1. The method of determining LDC for systems with limited solubility of components

In this case, the shape of the solidus and liquidus lines in the studied SD can be expressed with sufficient accuracy by second-order polynomials as functions of impurity concentrations:

$$T_S = p_{SB} \cdot x_{SB}^2 + q_{SB} \cdot x_{SB} + T_{MA} \quad (2)$$

$$T_L = p_{LB} \cdot x_{LB}^2 + q_{LB} \cdot x_{LB} + T_{MA}, \quad (3)$$

where x_{SB} , x_{LB} are concentrations of impurities in the solid and liquid phases in the approximating equations, at. %; p_{SB} , p_{LB} , q_{SB} , q_{LB} – regression coefficients, T_{MA} – melting temperature of the main component, T_S , T_L – temperatures on the solidus and liquidus lines, respectively.

Since EDC is an isothermal ratio of impurity concentration, then the expression for EDC as a function of impurity concentration is:

$$k_{OB} = \frac{p_{LB} \cdot x_{LB} + q_{LB}}{p_{SB} \cdot x_{SB} + q_{SB}} \quad (3)$$

The LDC of an impurity is defined as the limiting value of the equilibrium coefficient k_{OB}^A when $T \rightarrow T_{MA}$, or the concentration of the impurity ($x_{L,SB}$) $\rightarrow 0$:

$$k_{olimB} = \frac{q_{LB}}{q_{SB}} \quad (4)$$

In works [6, 7] the results of determination of LDC for individual impurities in cadmium, zinc and tellurium were presented. The regression coefficients were calculated using a computer using a developed algorithm using the method of least squares based on pairs of values taken from SD [8, 9]: $T_S(i)$, $x_{SB}(i)$ and $T_L(j)$, $x_{LB}(j)$.

Table 1 shows the values of the regression coefficients for the equations of the solidus and liquidus lines in the Cd, Zn – B systems and calculated by (4) k_{olimB}^A of the considered elements – impurities in the base.

Table 1

The values of the regression coefficients of the equations of the solidus and liquidus lines in the Cd, Zn – B systems and the limiting coefficients k_{olimB}^A

System	p_{SB}	q_{SB}	p_{LB}	q_{SL}	k_{olimB}^A
Cd–Zn	– 0,9621	– 8,9750	– 0,0800	– 3,1756	0,35
Cd–Sn	7,1146	– 42,0949	0,0440	– 4,0603	0,096
Cd–Hg	0,0144	– 6,2499	– 0,0583	– 2,6480	0,42
Zn–Al	23,3292	– 46,2323	0,2875	– 4,7623	0,1
Zn–Li	– 15,0546	– 21,8824	– 0,7632	– 4,2685	0,2

The method discussed above was also used by the authors to determine the LDC of individual elements and in other metals, such as Hf, Zr [10] and Ti [11].

3.2. Method for determining LDC for systems with extremely low solubility of components

The method of determining k_{olimB}^A by the method of mathematical analysis of SD described above is limited in its application to the type of SD, since metals with many elements have a very low solubility in the solid state (absence of the solidus line on SD, Fig. 1b). Therefore, for such systems, it is impossible to determine the LDC using this method. The problem of determining k_{olimB}^A for systems with extremely low solubility of impurity elements in the solid state was solved [7, 12].

The proposed calculation method consists in the mathematical analysis of only the liquidus line of known SD at the limit point at the melting temperature of the pure T_{MA} component, when $x_{LB} \rightarrow 0$ and using theoretical calculations to determine k_{OB}^A by thermodynamic parameters. In this case, similar to the above-described procedure for approximating the expression of the liquidus line SD (2), the parameter is found

$$\left(\frac{d\Delta T_L}{dx_{LB}} \right)_{x_{LB} \rightarrow 0} = -q_{LB}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta T_L = T_L - T_{MA}$, x_{LB} , q_{LB} – have the same value as in (2).

The well-known expression for determining the equilibrium distribution coefficient is [2]:

$$k_{OB}^A = 1 - \frac{\Delta H_{MA} \cdot (T_{MA} - T)}{R \cdot T_{MA} \cdot T \cdot x_{LB}}, \quad (6)$$

where T is the deviation temperature from T_{MA} , ΔH_{MA} is the melting enthalpy of the main component, R is the universal gas constant, x_{LB} is the mole fraction of the impurity concentration.

In the extreme case $T \rightarrow T_{MA}$, taking into account relation (5) and the transition from mole fractions to percentages, this expression can be transformed into the following form in its final form:

$$k_{olimB}^A = 1 + \frac{100 \cdot q_{LB} \cdot \Delta H_{MA}}{R \cdot T_{MA}^2}. \quad (8)$$

The resulting expression was used to calculate k_{olimB}^A in cadmium, zinc, tellurium and other metals [7, 12].

It should be noted that the proposed calculation method for determining LDC can also be used for systems with limited solubility. Compared with the well-known method of Kuchar et al. [1, 3, 5], the numerical calculations are reduced by a factor of two, and the range of systems for which k_{olimB}^A can be determined is significantly expanded.

4. Graphic methods of determining LDC

The graphical methods for determining k_{olimB}^A are based on the construction of graphs of the dependence of EDC on the concentration and temperature of dissolution of the components when these values approach the limit zero values.

The approximating equations (2), (3) make it possible to carry out a graphical representation of DS in the area of ultra-low concentrations of impurities, as well as to determine k_{olimB}^A graphically by extrapolation of the solidus and liquidus lines to zero concentration of the impurity and to determine the parameters (ΔT_{MA} and x_{LB}) of reaching the limit value. With such an extrapolation, k_{olimB}^A in the region of an ultrapure substance is determined uniquely and has its own characteristic value for each "element - impurity" system, which depends on the type of substance. In the usual representation of SD, it is not possible to obtain the relation between temperature and concentration in the region of ultrapure substances. For this, it is advisable to use the semi- and logarithmic scale of the image.

In fig. 2 shows a demonstration of liquidus and solidus curves of Zr–Bi, Zr–Cr systems in the semi- and logarithmic scale of the image [10]. It can be seen from the figure (left) that at $x_B < 0.1$ at.% the solidus and liquidus lines are parallel. This indicates that below this value, the limiting coefficient assumes a constant value. This value of concentration corresponds to a deviation from the melting temperature of $\Delta T_{MA} < 10$ °C (figure on the right). The insets show the dependence of k_{OB}^A on

the x_{SB} and x_{LB} concentrations and their limit values k_{0limB}^A . For the low concentrations, when displayed in the coordinates $\Delta T_{MA} = f(\lg x_{S,L})$, the solidus and liquidus lines are placed at a distance from each other:

$$\lg k_{0B}^A = \lg x_{SB} - \lg x_{LB}. \quad (9)$$

The k_{0limB}^A values obtained by this graphical method coincide with the calculated values [10]

Fig. 2.

The binary diagrams of the state Zr–Bi, Zr–Cr, in semi- and logarithmic coordinates and LDC k_{0limBi}^{Zr} , k_{0limCr}^{Zr} .

For the graphical method of determining of k_{0limB}^A , may be used another dependence of the equilibrium DC on the concentration of components and on the dissolution temperature. Such methods are described in works [1, 13]. For isothermal conditions, the following dependences of k_{0B}^A on concentration (10) and temperature (11) can be obtained from expressions (2) and (3):

$$k_{0B}^C = (p_{LB}x_{LB} + q_{LB}) / (p_{SB}x_{SB} + p_{SB}), \quad (10)$$

$$k_{0B}^T = \frac{p_{LB} \left(\pm \sqrt{q_{SB}^2 - 4p_{SB}\Delta T_{MA} - q_{SB}} \right)}{p_{SB} \left(\pm \sqrt{q_{LB}^2 - 4p_{LB}\Delta T_{MA} - q_{LB}} \right)}. \quad (11)$$

The parameters in expressions (10) and (11) have the same meanings as in (1) and (2).

It follows from expressions (2) and (3) that the DC can be represented in the form: $k_{0B}^A = f(x_S)$ and $k_{0B}^A = f(x_L)$. The extrapolation of these functions when $x_B \rightarrow 0$ allows determining the value of the LDC. In fig. 3 shows the dependence curves $k_{0B}^A = f(x_L, x_B)$ for binary systems Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge.

Fig. 3. The dependencies of EDC on the concentration of the second component in solid – 1 and liquid – 2 phases for binary systems Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge.

The curves have a different character depending on the curvature of the solidus and liquidus lines. However, they have a common point of intersection at $x_B \rightarrow 0$, which characterizes the specified limiting value of $k_{0 \text{ lim B}}^A$. The above calculations can be considered as an additional graphical method of determining the LDC and (or) it can be used to clarify and check the values of the limit coefficients obtained by other methods.

The fig. 4 shows the dependences of the ECR on ΔT_{MA} for the above-mentioned systems, constructed according to expression (11).

The analysis of the obtained dependencies shows that for the studied systems in the temperature range from the melting point of the main component of T_{MA} to the eutectic temperature of T_{EA} , a linear dependence of k_{0B}^T on ΔT_{MA} is observed. The points of intersection of the lines k_{0B}^T with the ordinate axis correspond to the values of $k_{0 \text{ lim B}}^A$ of the corresponding systems. In [13] it was shown that k_{0B}^C will also be characterized by its linear dependence on ΔT_{MA} .

Fig. 4. The dependence of EDC k_{0B}^T on ΔT_{MA} for Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge systems.

The analysis of the results (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4) shows that the values of LDC obtained by graphic methods for the studied systems completely coincide with each other.

This work presents the following binary metal systems: Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge. The choice of these systems is due to the fact that they belong to systems with limited solubility and they were studied for the purpose of calculating such thermodynamic values as partial enthalpy of dissolution $\Delta \bar{H}_B^G$, activity coefficients γ_B^G and activity of components a_B^G in these systems [14].

Conclusions

The characteristics of interphase DC of distribution of two-component metallic systems were given. Special attention is paid to the LDC of the impurity k_{0limB}^A , which characterizes the region of extremely dilute solutions when the concentration of the impurity element is reduced to zero.

The methods of determining the limiting coefficients of the distribution of component B in the base A k_{0limB}^A in metallic systems are described. The difference in approaches to LDC calculations for systems with limited solubility of components and systems with extremely low solubility of the second element was shown. Literature references and partial results of k_{0limB}^A calculations for binary systems based on Cd, Zn, Te, Zr, Hf and Ti with a small content of impurity elements are given.

The graphical methods for determining the limiting distribution coefficients for the Ag–Mg, Ni–Ga, Mg–Al, Nb–Ge systems are described. A complete coincidence of the results of LDC obtained by various graphical methods is shown.

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